

STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF VARIOUS FACTORS IN SCHOOLS ON THE PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Incompatibility of school equipment with age indicators, insufficient level of artificial lighting, delays in physical development, abrupt changes in training load, nutritional status, microclimate indicators are inextricably linked with an increase in the amount of dust and microbes.

Relevance of the topic: Physical education is a conscious activity aimed at maintaining and strengthening health. The development of physical education standards in schools and kindergartens should take into account the characteristics of the physical development of children and adolescents.

It is known that the health of schoolchildren and their physical development are largely formed under the influence of school factors, and at present their significance is becoming increasingly important.

A number of targeted scientific studies are being conducted around the world to substantiate the hygienic impact of school factors on the physical capabilities of students in hot climates. These studies assess the health status of schoolchildren based on medical examination materials, evaluate the microclimate, physical and chemical parameters of school premises in hot climates, the organization of the educational process, and the impact of school equipment on the physical development of students.

Solving these problems and improving hygiene recommendations aimed at increasing the number of students belonging to the first health group are one of the urgent tasks today.

Objective: Development and implementation of hygiene recommendations to improve factors influencing the physical development, capabilities and health of schoolchildren.

Research materials: The study used indicators of school students' morbidity, their learning and education conditions (microclimate parameters, equipment, quantity and size of

dust particles, school schedule), anthropometric indicators (for example, chest circumference, height and body weight of school students in the Republic of Karakalpakstan).

Results of the study: Many authors point to the deterioration of the somatic health and physical development of schoolchildren. In ecologically unfavorable zones during the period of active growth, functional changes and deterioration of children's health were recorded. In recent years, the environmental situation in the Southern Aral Sea region has significantly worsened, and, according to researchers, public health indicators continue to deteriorate. In the spring of 2022–2023, a somatometric examination of 15 adolescents aged 7–14 years from various regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan was conducted. It turned out that the total body volume of teenagers living in ecologically unfavorable areas was lower than that of their peers from ecologically "clean" zones.

Based on the data obtained, it was found that the height and weight of 14-year-old teenagers from the city of Muynak were statistically lower than their peers from Nukus and Tortkul. No statistically significant differences were found in the height and weight of 14-year-old teenagers, but the chest circumference of teenagers from Tortkul was higher than that of their peers from the other two districts.

Conclusion: Due to the imperfection of the body's protective functions, the greatest changes in health indicators occurred in children who were the first to react to the unfavorable environmental situation in the region. This is due to the high sensitivity of their body to the state of the environment.

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